

DEVELOPING PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF TEACHERS: STRATEGIES FOR CONTINUOUS GROWTH

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ABSTRACT

The article investigates the pivotal role played by developing professional competence of teachers and strategies for achieving this goal in teaching students for acquiring proficiency in a foreign language. The role of teachers in shaping the future of students cannot be overstated. Professional competence of teachers refers to the combination of knowledge, skills, attitudes, and behaviors that enable educators to effectively perform their roles in the classroom and beyond. It encompasses a range of qualities that contribute to high-quality teaching and student learning outcomes.

Key words: professional competence, continuous growth, mentoring and coaching, reflective practice.

Teachers play a crucial role in imparting knowledge, fostering critical thinking skills, and nurturing the overall development of students. Assessing a teacher's professional competence now includes considering their information competence, which involves the ability to effectively utilize information from educational disciplines and the broader world. Incorporating information technology in teacher training entails engaging teachers and students in an information-rich environment where communication is conducted using the tools and technologies of that environment. Developing information and technological competence involves using modern computer and communication technologies for communication and workflow organization. To cultivate this competence, specific pedagogical conditions must be created to enhance the information component of subjects taught by language teachers. This process equips teachers with the knowledge and skills to design and implement educational software, utilize systems for processing various types of information, access online databases, navigate the internet, participate in electronic conferences, and engage in real-time communication. Acquiring these competencies through the use of modern computer equipment and telecommunication resources enhances a teacher's professional skills and overall competence. In order to ensure high-quality education and student success, it is essential to focus on developing the professional competence of teachers. Continuous growth and improvement in teaching practices not only benefit teachers themselves but also have a direct impact on student learning outcomes. In this article, we will explore strategies for developing the professional competence of teachers to enhance the quality of education.

Continuous Professional Development (CPD):

Continuous Professional Development (CPD) is a key strategy for enhancing the professional competence of teachers. CPD involves engaging in ongoing learning opportunities such as workshops, conferences, online courses, and peer observation. By participating in CPD activities, teachers can stay current with best practices, innovative teaching methods, and educational trends. CPD also allows teachers to expand their knowledge base, develop new skills, and improve their teaching practices.

Mentoring and Coaching:

Mentoring and coaching are effective strategies for supporting the professional growth of teachers, especially newer teachers. Pairing experienced teachers with newer teachers can provide valuable guidance, support, and feedback. Mentors can share their expertise, offer advice on classroom management techniques, and help new teachers navigate challenges. Coaching sessions can focus on setting goals, reflecting on teaching practices, and developing action plans for improvement.

Reflective Practice:

Reflective practice is an essential component of professional development for teachers. Encouraging teachers to reflect on their teaching practices, identify strengths and areas for improvement, and set goals for professional growth can lead to increased self-awareness and better decision-making in the classroom. Reflective practice allows teachers to critically evaluate their teaching methods, assess student learning outcomes, and make adjustments to improve their instructional strategies.

Collaboration and Teamwork:

Fostering a culture of collaboration among teachers is another effective strategy for developing professional competence. Encouraging teachers to work together through team meetings, sharing resources, and engaging in collaborative lesson planning can lead to new ideas and approaches to teaching. Collaborative efforts can also create a supportive environment where teachers can learn from each other, share best practices, and collectively strive for continuous improvement.

Feedback and Evaluation:

Providing constructive feedback to teachers is essential for their professional growth. Feedback can come from classroom observations, student evaluations, and performance reviews. Constructive feedback helps teachers identify their strengths and areas for improvement, set goals for professional development, and make necessary adjustments to enhance their teaching practices. Regular feedback and evaluation can also help teachers track their progress, celebrate achievements, and address any challenges they may face.

Professional Learning Communities:

Participating in professional learning communities is another valuable strategy for developing the professional competence of teachers. Professional learning communities provide opportunities for teachers to collaborate with colleagues, share best practices, discuss educational trends and research, and engage in meaningful conversations about teaching and learning. By participating in professional learning communities, teachers can expand their knowledge base, stay informed about current educational practices, and enhance their teaching skills.

Technology Integration:

Incorporating technology into teaching practices is becoming increasingly important in today's digital age. Supporting teachers in integrating technology into their classrooms can enhance student engagement, facilitate personalized learning experiences, and improve learning outcomes. Providing training on educational technology tools and platforms can help teachers develop their digital literacy skills, explore new ways of delivering instruction, and adapt to the changing educational landscape.

To sum up, developing the professional competence of teachers is essential for ensuring high-quality education and student success. By implementing strategies such as continuous

professional development, mentoring and coaching, reflective practice, collaboration and teamwork, feedback and evaluation, participation in professional learning communities, and technology integration, schools can support teachers in their ongoing growth and development. Investing in the professional development of teachers not only benefits individual educators but also has a positive impact on student learning outcomes and overall school performance. By prioritizing the development of teacher competence, schools can create a culture of continuous improvement and excellence in education.

References:

1. A. M. Sanko, N. B. Strekalova. Professional competence of the teacher: test bank-Samara:Samara University Press, 2018.
2. Baidenko V.I., Competences in vocational education (towards the development of a competency-based approach) - 2004.
3. Botsmanova N. V. Development of professional competence in the system of secondary vocational education. VI International Scientific Conference "Theory and Practice of Education in the Modern World" –St,Peterburg, 2014.
4. Ivanov D.A. Competencies and competency-based approach in modern education, 2007